

VARIETIES OF DRIED GRAPES AND QUALITY INDICATORS

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Abstract: The article presents the technological aspects of producing dried grapes, including raisins, sultanas, and currants, which meet human physiological needs for essential nutrients and energy. The products must comply with established food safety and quality requirements, particularly regarding organoleptic and physicochemical parameters, and conform to relevant regulatory standards and normative documents.

Keywords: dried grapes, technology, processing method, raisins, sultanas, currants, standard, variety, color, taste, indicator, moisture.

As is well known, in the Republic dried grapes are produced from various grape varieties using different drying technologies and designs of drying equipment. Depending on the color of the berries, dried grapes are classified as light or dark. According to the applied processing technology, three main types of dried grapes are distinguished: raisins, sultanas (kishmish), and currants (korinka) [1].

Raisins are produced from seeded grape varieties such as Katta-Kurgan, Sultani, Charos, Rizamat-Ota, Mercedes, and others. There are two types of raisins: light and dark. Light raisins are obtained from light-colored grape varieties whose berries are pretreated with a weak alkaline solution and then dried either by the air-sun method or mechanically in various types of dryers. To preserve the light color, the raw grapes are treated with sulfur dioxide (SO₂) by wet or dry sulfitation. Previously, SO₂ was included in the list of safe chemicals and its use did not require strict control. However, based on medical research confirming its adverse effects on the human body, its content in food products is currently regulated. For example, the residual amount of SO₂ in grapes and grape products must not exceed 1500 mg/kg, as established by the Food Code [2–3].

Dark or black raisins are produced from red grape varieties and are dried by the air-sun or artificial method without preliminary treatment.

Kishmish (sultanas) are dried grapes obtained from seedless grape varieties. According to GOST 6882–88, four varieties of kishmish are distinguished: Soyagi, Sabza, Bedona, and Shigani [3]. Shigani is produced from dark grape varieties without preliminary treatment, including Kishmish “Botir,” Kishmish “Zarafshan,” Kishmish “Yubileiny,” Kishmish “Hishrau,” and others. The other three varieties are produced from white grape varieties such as Kishmish “Botir,” Kishmish “Zarafshan,” Kishmish “Duoba,” Kishmish “Hishrau,” Kishmish “Sogdiana,” and Kishmish “Samarkandskiy.”

Figure 1. Raisins “Rizamat Ota”

Figure 2. Raisins “Korinka”

Soyagi is dried in specialized facilities that prevent direct exposure to sunlight. In contrast, **Sabza** and **Bedona** are produced using either the air-sun drying method or mechanized drying techniques. In the production of *Sabza* dried grapes, the raw grapes are preliminarily treated with alkaline solutions and sulfur dioxide prior to the drying process.

Figure 3. Kishmish “Botir”

Figure 4. Kishmish “Zarafshan”

Figure 5. Kishmish "Duoba"

Figure 6. Kishmish "Hishrau"

Figure 7. Kishmish "Sogdiana"

Figure 8. Kishmish "Samarkandskiy" Currants or Corinthian Raisins

- получают исключительно из Seedless grape varieties of both dark and light types are used [4]. As a rule, the raw grapes are not subjected to preliminary treatment or sulfitation prior to drying (Figures 9-10).

Figure 9. Black Korinka

Figure 10. Light Korinka

Dried grapes must meet human physiological needs for essential nutrients and energy, comply with food product requirements in terms of organoleptic and physicochemical parameters, and conform to established regulatory documents and standards. Depending on quality indicators, dried grapes are classified into premium, first, and second grades.

However, regardless of grade, the finished product must satisfy the fundamental quality and organoleptic requirements. Raisins should possess the characteristic properties of products obtained from properly selected, fully ripened grape varieties, which are reflected in the color and texture specific to the variety. In terms of nutritional value, they should contain a high proportion of mature berries with elevated levels of sugars and essential nutrients. Dried grapes must not contain rotten or pest-damaged berries, berries showing signs of alcoholic fermentation or mold visible to the naked eye, nor berries that exhibit metallic taste or contain mineral impurities detectable by organoleptic evaluation.

Conclusions. The conducted analysis demonstrates that dried grapes produced from raisin and kishmish varieties intended for export must comply with international standards CAC/RCP 67-1981 and CAC/RS 67-1981. These products must exhibit the color, taste, and maturity index typical of the respective variety and meet the specified requirements for moisture content, which should not exceed 18–19%.

References:

1. Akopyan, L. L. (2016). The influence of certain quality indicators and technological parameters of dried grape production on the species composition of contaminant micromycetes and their toxigenicity. PhD Dissertation in Biological Sciences. Yerevan, 136 p.
2. Rakhmatov, O. (2025). Development and justification of the parameters of a destemmer for dried grapes. Ziyu Publishing House. Gulistan, 124 p.
3. GOST 6882–88. (2009). Dried grapes. Technical specifications. Characteristics of dried grape types. Interstate Standard. Moscow: Standartinform, pp. 1–8.
4. Rakhmatov, O., & Rakhmatov, F. (2023). Experimental study of the process of drying melon slices in a chamber-convection dryer. E3S Web of Conferences, Vol. 443, 02004. EDP Sciences.

5. Rakhmatov, O., Zhulbekov, I. S., & Kabulov, I. M. (2023). Experimental study of a drying installation for drying melon with IR radiation. *E3S Web of Conferences*, Vol. 443, 02005. EDP Sciences.
6. Rakhmatov, F. O., & Rakhmatov, O. (2023). Methodology for determining the heat balance and aerodynamic parameters of a drying installation. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(6), 90–94.
7. Rakhmatov, O., Rakhmatov, O., & Rakhmatov, F. (2024). Development and justification of the parameters of a destemmer for dried grapes. *BIO Web of Conferences*, Vol. 105, 04006. EDP Sciences.
8. Rakhmatov, O. (2024). Determination of the economic efficiency of a chamber-convective drying installation for melon drying. *Economics and Society*, (11-2 (126)), 810–814.
9. Theoretical and experimental analysis of the operation of a combined drying installation with IR radiation for drying agricultural products. *Ilm, Tadqiqot va Taraqqiyot Scientific Journal*, No. 5(13), Namangan, 2025, pp. 115–122.
10. Rakhmatov, O., Rakhmatov, F. O., & Rakhmatov, O. O. (2024, December). Laboratory studies of the process of drying melon slices by convective method. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Vol. 1420(1), 012010. IOP Publishing.
11. Rakhmatov, O., Baizakov, S. K., Rakhmatov, O. F., & Rakhmatov, O. O. (2024, December). Development of a combined drying plant for agricultural products. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Vol. 1420(1), 012014. IOP Publishing.
12. Final Report (2018). Research project on conducting pilot tests and implementation of an efficient resource-saving drying installation for fruit and melon crops, Contract No. I-

